

Determination of trace arginine by adsorptive voltammetry of its nickel(II) complex

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The adsorptive voltammetric wave of the arginine-nickel(II) complex is observed in 0.02 M borax buffer solution whose pH is adjusted to 8.5 by nitric acid. The complex is adsorbed strongly on the surface of hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE), giving a sensitive reduction peak at -0.82 V (vs SCE). A linear relationship holds between derivative peak height and the arginine concentration in the range 1.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm $^{-3}$. The detection limit is 5.0×10^{-9} mol dm $^{-3}$. The method has been applied to the detection of arginine in food samples. The mechanism of electrode reaction is discussed.

Many polarographic methods have been proposed for the detection of amino acids. But among natural amino acids, only cysteine and cystine can be determined directly by polarography¹. Other amino acids are electroinactive compounds and need to be carried out indirectly. Shvedene *et al.*² proposed a DPP method using the reaction that tyrosine is transformed into electroactive isoindols with 3 mM phthalaldehyde and 1 mM methionine by using d.c. polarography in the range 1×10^{-5} – 8×10^{-5} mol dm $^{-3}$. Moreira and Fogg⁴ proposed an electrochemical method to determine histidine of its Cu^{II} complex.

During the past twenty years, more and more adsorptive stripping voltammetric methods have been used due to its remarkable sensitivity, low cost and suitability to on-line measurement⁵. In the present paper, the adsorption characteristic of arginine-Ni^{II} complex at HMDE has been reported, together with a method for the voltammetric determination of trace arginine.

Fig. 1. Adsorption derivative voltammogram of Ni^{II}-arginine complex. (a) 0.02 mol dm $^{-3}$ borax, 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$ Ni^{II}, (b) a + 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm $^{-3}$ arginine; $E_a = -0.30$ V, $f_a = 60$ s, $V = 100$ mV s $^{-1}$

Results and Discussion

Voltammograms of Ni^{II}-arginine complex : No peak corresponding to the reduction of Ni^{II} or arginine appeared on the adsorption voltammogram between -0.40 to -1.0 V. However, in this potential range, the Ni^{II}-arginine complex can be reduced at the HMDE. The voltammogram is shown in Fig. 1. The peak potential of the reduction of the complex in 0.02 mol dm $^{-3}$ borax buffer solution is -0.82 V.

Optimum conditions : The voltammetric behaviour of the Ni^{II}-arginine complex was studied in ammonia-ammonium chloride, sodium biphosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, acetic acid-sodium acetate, and borax solution. The experimental results show that only in borax medium, a sensitive and well-defined reductive wave of the complex can be obtained. Therefore, borax was chosen as electrolyte at an optimum concentration of 0.02 mol dm $^{-3}$. pH was adjusted using 0.1 mol dm $^{-3}$ nitric acid and a pH of 8.5 was chosen as the best pH value in this experiment. At a constant arginine concentration, the quantity of Ni^{II} was changed in order to obtain a relationship between the peak current of the complex and the Ni^{II} concentration. The peak current was found to increase with increasing concentration of nickel ion. However, the wave was not stable when the concentration of Ni^{II} was higher than 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$. Hence, 5.0×10^{-5} mol dm $^{-3}$ was chosen as the Ni^{II} concentration. Peak current was found to increase with the negative shift of potential in the range from 0.0 to -0.4 V. So -0.40 V was chosen as the best accumulation potential.

Adsorptive voltammetric characteristics of the complex : In a certain range of accumulative time, the peak current increased linearly with the increase of accumulative time, which showed that complex had the adsorption characteristics on HMDE. When surfactants were added to the solution, such as cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB), cetyl pyridine bromide (CPB), and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), the peak current decreased. The surfactants

can be adsorbed on the HMDE and reduce the adsorption of the complex. This shows that the wave of the complex has relationship with adsorption. The results show that the peak current has a concave relationship with $V^{1/2}$. This indicates that the complex has adsorption characteristics on HMDE⁶. Fig. 2 shows that there is only one reductive wave at -0.82 V (vs SCE) and no corresponding anodic wave appears in the potential range -0.40 to -1.00 V. This implies that the electrode process is totally irreversible.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram : 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ Ni^{II}; other experimental conditions same as in Fig 1.

Electrode process : The overall electrode process in adsorption voltammetry can be divided into three steps : (i) homogeneous reaction in the bulk of the solution, $\text{Ni(II)} + 2\text{A} = \text{Ni(II)A}_2$, where A is arginine, (ii) adsorption accumulation of the complex, $\text{Ni(II)A}_2 = \text{Ni(II)A}_2(\text{ads})(\text{Hg})$, and (iii) reduction of the adsorbed reactant. In order to obtain some information on the reactant and products, electrolysis was performed. The working electrode was a mercury-cup electrode, and an electrolysis potential of -1.0 V was applied. After the reduction peak current of Ni(II)A_2 had dropped down to zero (number of electrons was calculated to be 2). The solution was transferred back into the cell and a defined amount of Ni^{II} was added to the cell. By using voltammetry, the peak corresponding to the reduction of Ni(II)A_2 ($E_p = -0.82$ V) was obtained again. It is evident that the reactant is Ni(II) in Ni(II)A_2 .

After voltammetric scan (from -0.40 to -1.0 V), the mercury drop was not removed and then the same accumulation procedure was applied. The reduction peak of Ni(II)A_2 was found to drop a little, which means that the product of Ni(II)A_2 was adsorbed on the mercury electrode. Considering the above facts, the electrode surface reaction can be expressed as : $\text{Ni(II)A}_2(\text{ads})(\text{Hg}) + 2e = \text{Ni(0)}(\text{Hg}) + 2\text{A}(\text{ads})$.

Analytical application : Under the optimum experimen-

tal conditions, a linear relationship holds between the peak current of the complex and arginine concentration in the range 1.0×10^{-8} – 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³. The detection limit is 5.0×10^{-9} mol dm⁻³. The results show a good selectivity of the method, and 50 times of lysine, cystein, cystine, serine, tryptophane and 20 times of proline, methionine do not interfere with the determination of 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³ arginine.

A certain amount of the sample was mixed with 4 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution (5 ml) and deaerated with nitrogen. After being hydrolyzed for ~ 24 h at 110° , the solution was adjusted to pH 8 using of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄. It was filtered and the filtrate was diluted to a certain volume and tested according to the above experimental method. The recovery was found to be 97.4–101.2%. The results of the contents of arginine in wheat flour and sanck condiment were found satisfactory.

Experimental

A voltammetric analyzer (model 79-1) was used in connection with a self-made cell, using a three-electrode system consisting of a hanging mercury drop electrode (extrusion type) as the working electrode, a Pt plate as the counter electrode and a SCE as the reference electrode.

All chemicals were of A.R. grade and used as such. Triple-distilled water was used in all experiments. The following solutions were used : 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ arginine stock solution (used by dilution), 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ nickel(II) standard solution, 0.2 mol dm⁻³ borax solution and 0.1 mol dm⁻³ nitric acid solution.

Procedure : An aliquot of arginine solution, 150 μ l of 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ nickel(II) standard solution (150 μ l) and the borax solution (3 ml) were transferred to a 50 ml electrolytic cell and the pH was adjusted to 8.5 by using the nitric acid solution. The volume was diluted to 30 ml with triple-distilled water. The solution was deaerated for ~ 5 min with nitrogen. The measurement was carried out after a pre-concentration step in which the solution was stirred for 60 s and equilibrated for 10 s. Then the derivation polarogram was recorded by scanning the potential from -0.40 to -1.0 V.

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